

**Results of a survey of experts in the field of
archaeology on their needs and attitudes
regarding the integrated digital presentation of
archaeological heritage**

Rezultati ispitivanja stručnjaka iz polja
arheologije o njihovim potrebama i stavovima u
integriranoj digitalnoj prezentaciji arheološke
baštine

dr sc Domagoj Tončinić (Department of Archaeology, Faculty of Humanities and Social
Sciences, University of Zagreb)

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7786-071X>

dr sc Goran Zlodi (Department of Information Sciences, Faculty of Humanities and Social
Sciences, University of Zagreb)

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0860-4469>

Sanja Budić Leto (Postgraduate Doctoral Programme in Archaeology, Faculty of Humanities and
Social Sciences, University of Zagreb)

ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9135-9817>

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Abstract

This paper examines the needs and attitudes of experts in the field of archaeology in Croatia towards integrated digital solutions for the presentation of archaeological finds and sites. Experts in the field of archaeology in Croatia use and/or develop the aforementioned solutions in their everyday professional practice. The lack of well-defined criteria for digital interpretation in archaeology necessitates an understanding of user needs, including the needs of professionals working in the field of archaeology. A quantitative user survey was conducted via an online questionnaire (September 2022 – May 2025) and included 53 respondents from museum institutions holding archaeological collections, archaeological research institutes, and higher education institutions. The questionnaire comprised three categories of heritage presentation: public digital databases for movable finds, databases for archaeological sites, and digital interpretation of heritage. The results indicate that respondents attach the greatest importance to metadata and functionalities that support their everyday professional activities, while secondary content (games, entertainment elements, etc.) is considered less important. The survey demonstrates the need within the professional archaeological community for the development of public digital databases that would integrate informational and interpretative content.

Sažetak

Rad ispituje potrebe i stavove stručnjaka iz područja arheologije u Hrvatskoj prema integriranim digitalnim rješenjima za prezentaciju arheoloških nalaza i nalazišta. Stručnjaci iz područja arheologije u Hrvatskoj navedena rješenja koriste i/ili kreiraju u svakodnevnom profesionalnom životu. Nedostatak razrađenih kriterija za digitalnu interpretaciju u arheologiji iziskuje uvid u potrebe korisnika, pa tako i potrebe stručnjaka iz područja arheologije. Kvantitativno ispitivanje korisnika je provedeno putem online anketnog upitnika (rujan 2022. - svibanj 2025. godine), a

obuhvatilo je 53 ispitanika iz muzejskih ustanova koje u fondusima imaju arheološke zbirke, znanstvenih arheoloških instituta te visokoobrazovnih ustanova. Upitnik je sadržavao tri kategorije prezentacije baštine: javne digitalne baze podataka za pokretne nalaze, baze podataka za arheološka nalazišta te digitalnu interpretaciju baštine. Rezultati pokazuju da ispitanici najveću važnost pridaju metapodacima i funkcionalnostima koje im koriste u svakodnevnom profesionalnom životu, dok sekundarne sadržaje (igre, zabavni elementi i sl.) smatraju manje bitnima. Ispitivanje pokazuje potrebu stručne arheološke javnosti za razvojem javnih digitalnih baza podataka koje bi objedinjavanje informativne i interpretativne sadržaje.

1. Introduction

Solutions for the presentation of digitised heritage are mostly focused on the process of creation and/or final products, i.e. digital solutions, but rarely take into account the needs of users, i.e. the target groups for whom these solutions are intended (Rahaman and Tan, 2011; Uzelac, 2010). The lack of developed criteria for digital interpretation has also been identified in scientific disciplines such as archaeology (Rahaman and Tan, 2011). Existing archaeological databases containing a large number of records are very important information tools for professionals (Langer, 2015; Fugère et al., 2020) and are used for research and scholarly work; however, they lack creative elements such as digital storytelling (narratives) that would stimulate interest and retain users' attention (Langer, 2015). The integration of interactive content based on virtual reality and/or augmented reality technologies, as well as 3D models, can enhance user engagement (Jeffrey, 2012; Bekić, 2016).

In **digital databases**, metadata do not serve solely as a technical description of finds and sites, but rather as a key infrastructure for representing the past. The selection of fields, category labels and levels of precision—from typology and dating to circumstances of discovery, etc.—determines what the archaeological past can become at all, that is, what can be searched, linked, visualised and interpreted. In this way, metadata function as a model of the past, rather than a neutral list of facts. In this sense, the analysis of experts' attitudes towards the importance of individual metadata elements constitutes a central part of this paper: it demonstrates how the archaeological community in Croatia envisions a desirable digital representation of the past and

which information it considers essential for integrated systems to truly support research, documentation, presentation and interpretation of heritage.

In **our approach**, we distinguish between the representation of the past (the metadata and model layer through which data are structured), presentation (the ways in which these structured data are displayed through interfaces and visualisations), and interpretation (the scholarly and professional interpretations derived from these displays and data by archaeologists and other users).

Like our colleagues worldwide, experts in the field of archaeology in Croatia today increasingly both require and have access to **integrated digital solutions** for the presentation of archaeological finds and sites. Moreover, they themselves participate in the conceptualisation and development of solutions for presenting digitised heritage. Depending on the needs of their everyday professional practice, they use and/or create digital databases for movable finds, databases of archaeological sites, and digital interpretations of heritage.

Among digital databases for movable finds, three databases dedicated to epigraphic monuments should be highlighted: the *Epigraphische Datenbank Heidelberg* (edh-www.adw.uni-heidelberg.de/), *Ubi Erat Lupa – Bilddatenbank zu antiken Steindenkmälern* (lupa.at/), and *EDCS – Epigraphik-Datenbank Clauss / Slaby* (manfredclauss.de/). Owing to the possibility of searching these databases by various categories, including parts of inscriptions, the detailed cataloguing of inscriptions and entire monuments—which encompasses all elements of a classical catalogue—the inclusion of images of monuments, maps of findspots and places of storage, as well as the interconnection of databases, that is, of monuments published across all of them, research into, interpretation of, and publication of new Roman inscriptions are today inconceivable without their use. For other categories of movable finds, the comparable database *Artefacts – Encyclopédie collaborative en ligne des objets archéologiques* (artefacts.mom.fr) should also be mentioned. Archaeological professionals in Croatia make extensive use of these and other databases; however, the “blank areas” on their maps of findspots and distribution suggest that finds from the territory of Croatia are being incorporated into digital databases of movable finds only slowly. At the same time, there are currently no comparable databases in Croatia. Nevertheless, the national portal *eKultura* (ekultura.hr/) and projects involving the creation of online catalogues and the digitisation of museum collections—such as the *Online Catalogue of the Collections of the Archaeological Museum in Split* ([katalog-](#)

zbirke.armus.hr/hr/)—should be noted. For the time being, these include only a small number of archaeological finds or exhibits and are therefore aimed more at the general than at the professional public.

In contrast to digital databases of movable finds, experts in the field of archaeology in Croatia use digital databases of archaeological sites as part of their everyday professional needs not only for research, interpretation, and the publication of new research results, but also for the presentation and popularisation of their work and its outcomes. Digital databases of archaeological sites—whether archaeological maps, databases dedicated to sites within a particular geographical area, “thematic” databases devoted to related sites, or databases focused on a single site—constitute highly valuable tools for research, interpretation, and the dissemination of new research results. In the category of archaeological maps, the *Database of Ancient Archaeological Sites of the Republic of Croatia of the Institute of Archaeology* (BAZA) (baza.iarh.hr/public/locality/map) should be highlighted as one of the starting points for research into individual ancient sites in Croatia. Among “thematic” databases devoted to related sites, the *Roman Legionary Fortresses database* (legionaryfortresses.info/index.htm), with its map, bibliography, and ground plans of Roman legionary forts, deserves particular mention. In Croatia, two databases dedicated to Roman military sites along the Dalmatian and Danube Limes are especially noteworthy. The first is the database of the project *Between the Danube and the Mediterranean. Exploring the role of the Roman military in the mobility of people and goods in Croatia during the Roman Era – RoMiCRO* (IP-2013-11-6505), which provides an overview of Roman military sites as well as the units and monuments documented at them (ffzg.unizg.hr/romicro/?page_id=826&lang=hr). The *Danube Limes in Croatia* database of the Archaeological Museum in Osijek (<https://limescroatia.eu/links/>) offers an overview of sites and the history of research along the Danube Limes in Croatia. Although also a “thematic” database devoted to Roman sites along the Danube limes, it additionally includes data on the results of individual excavations as well as on finds. It is comparable to another, considerably more developed regional database on the Roman Danube Limes, *Der römische Limes in Österreich* (limes.univie.ac.at/html/world_heritage_1_1.php). Both examples also point to the problems that arise when digital databases of archaeological sites (or finds) move beyond the scope of their original project- or institution-based funding, along with the associated maintenance and updating of data. The Danube Limes in Croatia digital database, which includes individual

images of digital reconstructions of excavated architecture, also contains elements of digital heritage interpretation. Among the rare examples of digital heritage interpretation within public digital databases, the 3D models of individual archaeological exhibits in Croatia available on the national eKultura portal should be mentioned. By contrast, online 3D models of sites and architectural structures in Croatia, as well as virtual tours of archaeological sites—such as those available for Viminacium (<http://viminacium.org.rs/izlozbe/viminacium-virtual-tour/>)—are entirely lacking for Croatian sites.

2. Methods

This paper examines **the need within the professional archaeological community in Croatia** for an integrated digital solution that would combine information tools and narratives within a single system. The study was conducted using a questionnaire survey in Google Forms format, which was distributed to various Croatian institutions: museums, faculties and archaeological institutes, resulting in a total of 53 respondents. The use of online questionnaires has become a widespread practice in the field of heritage and museum studies, and user needs in the digital environment represent an important research topic (Zlodi, 2014). **The survey**, entitled *Survey for the purpose of researching the integrated digital presentation of archaeological heritage: content and functionalities*, was divided into three categories of questions: socio-demographic data; public archaeological databases dedicated to movable finds and sites; and digital interpretation of heritage. Each type of content included questions to which respondents answered using a Likert scale (1 – unimportant, 5 – very important) as well as open-ended questions.

2.1 Research design

The research was conducted as an **exploratory, cross-sectional survey** aimed at identifying experts' needs and attitudes regarding the content and functionalities of an integrated digital presentation of archaeological heritage. An **online questionnaire** was selected because it enables rapid distribution to the professional community across different institutions and facilitates the collection of structured and comparable data.

2.2 Instrument

The survey, entitled *Survey for the purpose of researching the integrated digital presentation of archaeological heritage: content and functionalities (Anketa u svrhu istraživanja integrirane digitalne prezentacije arheološke baštine: sadržaj i funkcionalnosti)*, was divided into three categories of questions. The questionnaire was created using the Google Forms application and consists of **36 closed-ended** and **3 open-ended** questions, grouped into three sections: 1) socio-demographic data; 2) public archaeological databases dedicated to a) movable finds and b) sites; and 3) digital interpretation of heritage.

The questions were developed on the basis of the literature (Rahaman and Tan, 2011) and the *A self-evaluation questionnaire for planning a user-centred web application* (pp. 121–126) and the *Websites and portals feedback form* (pp. 127–134), both from the *Handbook on Cultural Web User Interaction*. Rome: Minerva EC (2008).

Each type of content included questions to which respondents answered using a Likert scale (1 – unimportant, 5 – very important) and provided free-text responses to open-ended questions. The open-ended questions in this exploratory study were intended to capture the diverse perspectives of participants.

A pilot study was conducted in 2021 as part of the scientific conference *Salona between the Mediterranean and Pannonia*, organised by the Croatian Archaeological Society. A total of 32 conference participants were surveyed with the aim of gaining an initial insight into the need for creating a digital solution for the presentation of archaeological sites and finds. The majority of respondents from this population, 93.75%, considered that a digital solution integrating all key elements of research (information on archaeological research and the site, site history, a catalogue of finds, and relevant literature and online sources) would be useful and practical for scholarly research work. Based on this pilot study, insights were obtained that contributed to shaping the questions of the survey conducted within the framework of the present research.

2.3 Population

The target population comprises **professionals who are engaged in archaeology in Croatia**—

museum curators, institute staff, university lecturers, researchers and external collaborators associated with archaeology.

Most respondents belong to the 35–44 age group (50.9%), followed by the 25–34 age group (22.6%) and the 45–54 age group (15.1%). The smallest proportions of respondents belong to the 55–64 age group (7.5%) and the 65+ age group (3.8%). All respondents (a total of 53) are highly educated. The largest proportion hold a professional master's degree (64.2%), followed by holders of a doctoral degree (22.6%) and holders of a research master's degree (13.2%).

Please indicate your age group

53 responses

Please indicate your highest level of education

53 responses

1. Graphical representation of the age and educational structure of the respondents (The survey was conducted in Croatian, and for the purposes of this article the selected charts have been translated into English.)

According to the **type of institution** in which they are employed, the majority of respondents work in museums (84.9%), followed by faculties (7.5%) and scientific research institutes (3.8%). A smaller proportion (3.8%) are employed in private archaeological companies or are retired.

Within the **socio-demographic group** of questions, respondents were given the opportunity to state their specific interests in archaeology, which was taken up by 51 out of 53 respondents. Most indicated that they are primarily engaged in fieldwork and research, as well as in the analysis of movable archaeological material. Specific interests also include working with GIS systems, as well as educational and exhibition activities. Among the responses, interests in photographic documentation, methodology and archaeometry were also highlighted. The periods of interest among respondents are Antiquity (41.5%), the Middle Ages (28.3%), Prehistory (20.8%) and the Early Modern period (9.4%).

Please select the type of institution you work for
53 responses

2. Graphical representation of the surveyed population by place of employment (The survey was conducted in Croatian, and for the purposes of this article the selected charts have been translated into English.)

2.4 Sample

The sampling method was **convenience sampling**, which in this context means that individuals who were relatively easily accessible to the researchers (for example, professional colleagues

and experts from well-known institutions) were included in the study. The invitation to participate was distributed via professional mailing lists provided for the purpose of the research by the Museum Documentation Centre, as well as through the researchers' internal professional networks. The sample is therefore non-random (non-probabilistic), meaning that participants were not selected randomly from the wider population, but were invited in a targeted manner or accessed the survey independently based on their interest in and the relevance of the topic. A partly self-selection element is also present, as invited respondents independently decided whether to participate, which reduces systematic selection bias on the part of the researchers. The sample size was $N = 53$ completed questionnaires, which is acceptable for the exploratory purpose of this study. The **response rate was 34.86%**, calculated based on the number of professionals contacted and those who completed the survey. Accordingly, the sample is not representative of the population under study, and the characteristics of the sample cannot be generalised to the entire population. This, however, is not the aim of this exploratory research, whose purpose is to gain insights into a new and insufficiently researched topic.

2.5 Data collection procedure

The questionnaire was open from September 2022 to May 2025. At the beginning of the survey, participants were provided with an explanation of the purpose of the research, information on the time required to complete the questionnaire (15 minutes), and information regarding the anonymity of personal data and the confidentiality of responses. They were also informed that the survey results would be used exclusively for research purposes, for the preparation of a doctoral dissertation, and for the publication of scientific and professional outputs derived from the research. Participants were further informed that the data would be stored for as long as necessary to fulfil the stated purposes. No data other than the statistical results of the survey will be published or made available. The data were exported from the Google Forms application in CSV format for further analysis.

2.6 Ethics

The research was conducted in accordance with standard ethical norms of scientific research. Only anonymous data were collected; IP addresses and identifiers were not stored. The research

was approved on 29 April 2022 by the Ethics Committee for Scientific Research of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, University of Zagreb.

2.7 Data analysis methods

The following data analysis methods were employed in the study:

Descriptive statistics (e.g. frequencies, percentages and arithmetic means for individual variables) provide insight into respondents' attitudes and interests, which can be generalised in relation to the surveyed population.

Analysis of the frequency of importance attributed to metadata (e.g. ranking average scores for each metadata element related to movable finds and sites) enables the creation of a list of respondents' individual preferences.

Qualitative analysis of open-ended responses is particularly valuable due to the nature of this research, which addresses an under-researched topic and is therefore exploratory in character, allowing insight into individual attitudes and interests of respondents.

Visualisation – graphical representation of key data analyses.

2.8 Methodology: description of the sample and categories of questions

2.8.1 Categories of questions

Questions relating to the content and functionalities of public digital archaeological databases were divided into a segment examining users' attitudes towards databases for the presentation of movable archaeological finds and sites, while the final group of questions examined users' attitudes towards the digital interpretation of heritage.

The first group contains five questions, three of which offer multiple-choice options evaluated on a scale from 1 – unimportant to 5 – very important, while two questions are optional and open-ended. The first multiple-choice question reads: “Please assess the importance of the listed metadata in public digital databases for the presentation of archaeological finds that you use for work and research purposes,” and asks respondents to rate, on a scale from 1 to 5, 24 metadata

elements: inventory number, object type, object description, notes/remarks, dimensions and weight, material, object colour, production technique, object typology, state of preservation, period of manufacture, dating, cultural attribution, place of discovery (country, region, settlement), field coordinates of the find, details of discovery, discovery data (stratigraphic layer, quadrant, trench), discovery method, circumstances of discovery, place of manufacture, inscription transcription, inscription translation, list of relevant literature with links, and in-text references.

The second question is open-ended and reads: “Please enter other metadata that you consider important for your work and research (if any).”

The third question again offers multiple-choice options and reads: “Please assess the importance of related content in public digital archaeological databases that relates to movable finds,” where respondents rate, on a scale from 1 to 5, the importance of object photographs, object drawings, 3D object models, and a timeline with associated dates.

The fourth question reads: “Please assess the importance of functionalities in public digital archaeological databases that relate to movable finds,” where respondents rate, on a scale from 1 to 5, the importance of a total of eight functionalities: links to controlled vocabularies (thesaurus, glossary, etc.), access to definitions (scope notes) of controlled vocabularies, explanations of individual categories and terms (index), map display (GIS), user instructions and guidelines, data export options (QR code/JSON/XML/GeoJSON/PDF/RDF/representations), deep zoom of photographs (IIIF standard), and multilingualism.

The final question is optional and open-ended and reads: “Please enter other functionalities that you consider important for your work and research (if any).”

The second group of questions is designed in the same way, but presents respondents with different types of metadata, content and functionalities related to archaeological sites. It also contains five questions, the first of which asks respondents to assess metadata on a scale from 1 to 5 and reads: “Please assess the importance of metadata in public digital databases for the presentation of archaeological sites that you use for work and research purposes.” Respondents were asked to rate the following metadata: contemporary site name, historical site name, toponym, dating, country/region, coordinates, type of site or structure (settlement, cemetery, military camp, sacred building, etc.), function of the site or structure (workshop, temple, residential building, etc.), total area of the site or structure, excavated area of the site or structure,

type of archaeological research conducted, seasons of archaeological research, name of the project director, protection status, and a list of relevant literature with links to online publications.

The second question allows respondents to list additional important metadata if they believe such metadata exist. As in the group of questions relating to movable finds, the third question in the group examining professional attitudes towards the presentation of archaeological sites asks respondents to “assess the importance of related content in public digital archaeological databases that relates to archaeological sites.” The proposed related content includes: photographs, field drawings, field documentation, a timeline with associated dates, 3D models of sites and architectural structures, related websites, visitor information, and infrastructure available at the site.

The fourth question reads: “Please assess the importance of functionalities in public digital archaeological databases that relate to archaeological sites,” and examines attitudes towards the following functionalities: links to controlled vocabularies (thesaurus, glossary, etc.), access to definitions (scope notes) of controlled vocabularies, explanations of individual categories and terms (index), map display (GIS), user instructions and guidelines, data export options (QR code/JSON/XML/GeoJSON/PDF/RDF/representations), deep zoom of photographs (IIIF standard), and multilingualism.

The final question in this group allows respondents to enter additional functionalities that they personally consider important.

The final category of questions relates to users’ attitudes towards the digital interpretation of heritage, more specifically towards individual content types and aspects of presentation. The first of three questions in this group reads: “Please assess the importance of individual content types in the public digital interpretation of heritage that you use for work and scientific research purposes,” and respondents rate, on a scale from 1 to 5, the importance of thirteen content types: textual interpretation, photographs/photo albums, video recordings/video albums, virtual tours (360-degree panoramas), interactive 3D models, visualisations, references to data sources, blog, forum, social media, FAQ (frequently asked questions), games, and a user comments section. The second question asks respondents to assess the importance of specific aspects of digital heritage interpretation, such as: unique content, new information, source credibility, ease of use, entertainment potential, emotional engagement, aesthetic impression, applicability in

professional life, and applicability in private life.

The final question in this group reads: “Please indicate for which purposes you would use the presentation and interpretation of archaeological sites and finds,” offering respondents the option to select one or more of the following answers: research, publication of professional and scientific papers, preparation for teaching units, lifelong learning, leisure, and tourism.

3. Results of the survey of the professional community on public digital databases for the presentation of movable finds and sites

The conducted research reveals the needs and interests of respondents from the professional community, who use various public databases in their professional life and daily work, for example, in preparing teaching units, writing professional and scientific papers, preparing for field research, processing artefacts, and similar tasks.

3.1 Results of the survey of the professional community on public digital databases for the presentation of movable finds

3.1.1 Analysis of the importance of metadata

Respondents considered **metadata** related to the inventory number, object type and description, material, period and dating of manufacture, cultural attribution, and metadata concerning the place, circumstances, and method of discovery to be very important. Transcriptions and translations of inscriptions were also rated as very important.

Metadata related to the physical characteristics of objects, such as dimensions and weight, colour, and production technique, received slightly lower ratings, ranging from important to moderately important. For movable finds, notes/remarks, object typology, state of preservation,

field coordinates, place of manufacture, lists of relevant literature with links, and in-text references were considered of medium importance.

A small number of respondents rated individual metadata as “slightly important” or “unimportant,” most frequently for in-text references, notes/remarks, and object colour.

Respondents were also given the opportunity to add metadata they considered important but that were not listed. Among these, the “storage location of the object” was highlighted.

3.1.2 Analysis of the importance of related content

Among the **related content**, photographs received the highest rating of “very important,” with 46 respondents giving this rating, while 7 rated object photographs as “important.” Following in importance were object drawings, which received predominantly “very important” and “important” ratings. 3D models of objects and timelines with associated dates were rated with medium importance, receiving ratings of “important” or “moderately important.”

Please assess the importance of related content in public digital archaeological databases that pertains to movable finds.

53 responses

3. Graphical representation of the survey on the importance of related content in public digital databases for movable finds (The survey was conducted in Croatian, and for the purposes of this article the selected charts have been translated into English.)

3.1.3 Analysis of the importance of functionalities

The **functionalities** rated highest as “very important” were data export options and deep zoom. Functionalities considered “important” included explanations of individual categories and terms

(index), map display (GIS), user instructions and guidelines, and multilingual support. Two functionalities—links to controlled vocabularies (thesaurus, glossary, etc.) and access to definitions (scope notes) of controlled vocabularies—received medium ratings of “moderately important.”

Respondents were also given the opportunity to provide their own answers, and one highlighted the importance of “open access” databases, aligning with recommendations for contemporary practices in the humanities (Barbir, 2020).

3.2 Results of the survey of the professional community on public digital databases for the presentation of archaeological sites

3.2.1 Analysis of the importance of metadata

Among fifteen different types of metadata, the highest ratings were given to those related to the site’s nomenclature. Respondents considered the contemporary and historical site names, as well as the toponym, as “very important” or “important.” Dating of the site was also rated very important, with 35 respondents assigning a score of 5 (“very important”) and 18 a score of 4 (“important”). Metadata such as the country/region where the site is located and the type of site (settlement, cemetery, military camp, sacred building, etc.) were also considered very important, and the site’s function (workshop, temple, residential building, etc.) received high ratings. Metadata most frequently rated as “important” rather than “very important” included coordinates, total site area, excavated area, and information on conducted archaeological research: type of research, research seasons, and project director. Interestingly, respondents rated the protection status of the site as “very important,” while the list of relevant literature with links to online publications was considered “important.”

3.2.2 Analysis of the importance of related content

The most important related content in public digital databases for presenting archaeological sites was undoubtedly photographs, with 39 respondents rating them as “very important” and 14 as

“important.” Following in importance were field drawings and documentation, while timelines with associated dates, 3D models of sites and structures, and related websites were rated as “important.” Information for visitors was also included among the related content and was generally rated as “very important” or “important” by respondents.

3.2.3 Analysis of the importance of functionalities

The highest-rated functionalities, with the largest number of “very important” and slightly fewer “important” responses, were “data export options (QR code/JSON/XML/GeoJSON/PDF/RDF/representations)” and “deep zoom of photographs (IIIF standard).” Functionalities such as map display (GIS), user instructions and guidelines, and multilingual support were rated as “important,” while links to controlled vocabularies, definitions of controlled vocabularies, and explanations of individual categories and terms (index) received nearly equal numbers of “important” and “moderately important” responses. Respondents were also given the opportunity to add related content they considered important, and one respondent highlighted the “availability of georeferenced site plans in standard formats (SHP, DXF).”

4. Results of the survey of the professional community on public digital heritage interpretation

The conducted research examines the views of respondents from the professional community regarding the use of digital heritage interpretation within public digital databases, specifically investigating the need for the integration of such content into these databases.

4.1 Analysis of the importance of individual content types in public digital heritage interpretation

Respondents were asked to rate, on a scale from 1 (“not important”) to 5 (“very important”), the importance of different types of content appearing in public digital heritage presentations that could support their professional and research work.

Photographs/photo albums received the highest ratings and were the only content type with the majority of respondents assigning a score of 5 (“very important”). The next highest-rated content type was textual interpretation, although more respondents rated it 4 (“important”). Content types such as video recordings/video albums, virtual tours, interactive 3D models, visualizations, and references to data sources were predominantly rated as “important.” Medium ratings (“moderately important”) were given to content types aimed at user assistance, orientation, and interaction, including blogs, forums, social media, FAQs, games, and sections for user comments.

4.2 Analysis of the importance of specific aspects of digital heritage interpretation

Among the proposed aspects of digital heritage interpretation, “source credibility” and “ease of use” received the highest rating of “very important.” Aspects such as aesthetic appeal and provision of new information were also considered very important by most respondents. Unique content, entertainment value, emotional engagement, and applicability in private life received an average rating of 4 (“important”). The aspect of applying digital heritage interpretation in professional life received an equal number of ratings for “important” and “very important” (19 each), while a smaller number of respondents considered this aspect slightly or moderately important.

4.3 Analysis of the purposefulness of the presentation and interpretation of archaeological sites and finds

In the final survey question, respondents were asked to select one or more purposes for which the professional community generally uses the presentation and interpretation of archaeological sites

and finds. The majority, 48 respondents (90.6%), indicated that such interpretations are used for research purposes. A large number, 45 respondents (84.9%), reported using them for publishing professional and scientific papers. Fewer respondents indicated usage for preparing teaching units (22 respondents, 41.5%), lifelong learning (20 respondents, 37.7%), and leisure activities (19 respondents, 35.8%). Finally, a significant number, 39 respondents (73.6%), reported using the content for tourism purposes.

Please indicate the purposes for which you would use the presentation and interpretation of archaeological sites and finds.

53 responses

4. Graphical representation of the purposefulness of digital presentation and interpretation of archaeological sites and finds (The survey was conducted in Croatian, and for the purposes of this article the selected charts have been translated into English.)

5. Conclusion

Various theoretical models and metadata schemas (CIDOC-CRM, SPECNUM, Nomisma.org) are applied in heritage digitization practices; however, this study combines these frameworks with the concrete needs and critical reflections of end-users.

The study examines the needs and attitudes of Croatian professionals in the field of archaeology regarding integrated digital solutions for the presentation of archaeological heritage. The survey was conducted via an online questionnaire distributed to staff at museums, universities, and research institutes. A total of 53 archaeology professionals responded, providing their views on three thematic areas: public digital databases for movable finds, public digital databases for archaeological sites, and digital heritage interpretation.

The results indicate that Croatian archaeology professionals place the highest value on metadata related to the identification, context, and documentation of finds and sites, while the key functionalities highlighted include data export options and detailed viewing capabilities (deep zoom and GIS display). Photographs, textual content/interpretations, and source credibility are considered highly important, whereas interactive and entertainment elements are regarded as secondary. These findings align with recent insights into the role and application of contemporary information technologies in documenting archaeological heritage (Milošević, 2019).

Respondents reported frequent use of heritage presentation and interpretation for research purposes, but also recognized their importance as tools for lifelong learning and applications in tourism (Bekić, 2016). It can be concluded that the professional community demonstrates a clear need for publicly accessible digital platforms that integrate all essential professional informational tools and content.

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Artefacts – Encyclopédie collaborative en ligne des objets archéologiques

artefacts.mom.fr/

Baza antičkih arheoloških lokaliteta Republike Hrvatske Instituta za arheologiju (BAZA)

baza.iarh.hr/public/locality/map

Between the Danube and the Mediterranean. Exploring the role of Roman military in the mobility of people and goods in Croatia during the Roman Era – RoMiCRO (IP-2013-11-6505)

ffzg.unizg.hr/romicro/?page_id=826&lang=hr

Danube Limes in Croatia Arheološkog muzeja u Osijeku

limescroatia.eu/links/

Der römische Limes in Österreich

limes.univie.ac.at/html/world_heritage_1_1.php

EDCS – Epigraphik-Datenbank Clauss / Slaby

manfredclauss.de/

eKultura

ekultura.hr/

Epigraphische Datenbank Heidelberg

edh-www.adw.uni-heidelberg.de/

Mrežni katalog zbirke Arheološkog muzeja u Splitu

katalog-zbirke.armus.hr/hr/

Roman Legionary Fortresses

legionaryfortresses.info/index.htm

Ubi Erat Lupa – Bilddatenbank zu antiken Steindenkmälern

lupa.at/

Viminacium Virtual Tour

viminacium.org.rs/izlozbe/viminacium-virtual-tour/